

PERFORATION AND PENETRATION MECHANICS OF COMPOSITES: THEORY, EXPERIMENT AND FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Bazle Z. (Gama) Haque¹

¹Senior Structural Aerospace Engineer, Mclaurin Aerospace, Jacobs JETS II Contract
NASA Johnson Space Center, 2101 NASA Pkwy, B13-230, Houston, TX 77058, USA
Email: bazle.z.haque@nasa.gov, bzhaque@udel.edu

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ABSTRACT

Transverse impact of right circular cylinder (RCC) projectiles on finite-thickness thick and thin composite laminates are of great importance in understanding the mechanics and physics of lightweight protection materials. The fundamental objective is to optimize the deceleration of the impactor as a function of energy dissipating materials damage mechanisms in space and time following the conservation of energy and momentum.

Quasi-static punch shear test (QS-PST) experimental methodology had been developed by the author in quantifying the energy dissipating quasi-static perforation and penetration damage mechanisms of 1 to 24 layers (L) of plain weave (PW) 24 oz/yd² S-2 Glass/SC-15 composites. Ballistic limit experiments had been conducted on 24L and 32L thick laminates and then sectioned in understanding the ballistic damage mechanisms. It had been identified that the ballistic damage mechanisms can be simulated by the QS-PST experiments. By conducting QS-PST experiments as a function of punch diameter to support diameter ratio (SPR) and superimposing the experimental load-displacements, an envelope penetration curve had been constructed to represent 70% of the ballistic energy. A quasi-static model of ballistic penetration has been developed which also utilizes the maximum force from QS-PST experiment at SPR = 0 aka QS-Indentation (QSI) experiment and using a dynamic increase factor DIF = 1.1 yields 100% of the ballistic energy.

Finite element analysis of ballistic experiments for 11L, 24L, and 32L PW S-2 Glass/SC15 composites had been performed using rate dependent progressive composite damage model MAT162 in LS-DYNA in determining the time history of penetration resistance force and projectile dynamics. MAT162 progressive composite damage model has been proven to capture the ballistic damage mechanisms and had been validated for several composite materials.

The validated FE models are then used to simulate the ballistic limit analysis of very thick to thin e.g., 88L, 66L, 44L, 32L, 24L, 12L, 8L, 4L, & 2L PW S-2 Glass/SC15 composite laminates. From these simulations, three phases of ballistic penetration had been identified, i.e., (i) Penetration or P-phase, (ii) Transition or T-phase, and (iii) Perforation or F-phase. Calculating the through-thickness longitudinal wave velocity it has been postulated that the end of P-phase is complete when the shock wave reflects from the rear face of the target and meets the penetration front.

The classic penetration resistance test had been modified in understanding the P-phase of ballistic penetration and is termed as Depth of Penetration (DoP) test. An energy based theoretical model for the DoP experiments had been developed in calculating the characteristic time of DoP, impact contact force and projectile dynamics. A threshold velocity of penetration V_{TH} has been defined when the projectile will cease to penetrate the target. During the ballistic penetration and perforation of a finite thickness target, when the projectile velocity reduces to V_{TH} , the projectile continues to deform the remaining target and predominantly fails under tension-shear damage mechanism which is termed as the perforation or F-phase.

The relative thickness of a composite laminate has been defined based on the different phases of ballistic penetration. A thin laminate is defined as a laminate which only shows the perforation or F-phase (1L to 10L of PW S-2 Glass/SC15). An intermediate thickness laminate is defined which shows

both the transition or T-phase and perforation or F-phase of ballistic penetration (10L to 30L of PW S-2 Glass/SC15). A thick section composite laminate is defined where all three penetration phases are present, i.e., P-phase, T-phase, and F-phase (.GT. 30L of PW S-2 Glass/SC15).

Phoenix and Porwal (2003) have developed a 2D membrane theory which has been used to validate FE models for orthotropic composite materials in calculating the deformation cone/kink wave and bending wave velocities.

While the energy dissipating perforation damage mechanisms can be represented by QS-PST experiments, the penetration phase or P-phase damage mechanisms have been investigated by modifying the QSI experiments. The quasi-static indentation (QSI) strength X_{QSI} have been identified as a vital experiment in relative ranking of composite materials.

DoP experiments, QSI experiments, QS-PST experiments, ballistic limit experiments presented in this paper can quantify the energy dissipating penetration and perforation damage mechanisms. Theoretical models and LS-DYNA MAT162 computational analysis have provided insight in to the penetration and perforation of composites.

1 PERFORATION MECHANICS OF THIN-SECTION COMPOSITES

Transverse impact of a right circular cylinder (RCC) projectile on a 2D isotropic membrane is a good example of perforation (Phoenix & Porwal (P&P), 2003, [1]); in which, the thickness t_m of the membrane is considered much smaller than the diameter $D_p = 2r_p$ of the projectile, i.e., $t_m/D_p \ll 1$. For constant impact velocity V_p on a 2D membrane (Fig. 1), the axial/implosion membrane strain $\tilde{\varepsilon}_t(\tilde{r})$ can be expressed in terms of 1D implosion strain ε_0 and 1D cone/kink wave velocity $c_{k,0}$ in the material coordinate system as: $\tilde{\varepsilon}_t(\tilde{r}) = \varepsilon_0(r_s/\tilde{r}) \approx \alpha_0^2(r_s/\tilde{r})$, $r_k < \tilde{r} < r_s$, where $\alpha_0 = c_{k,0}/a_0 \approx \sqrt{\varepsilon_0} \approx (V_p/a_0\sqrt{2})^{2/3}$. The membrane strain in the cone wave region can be expressed as: $\varepsilon_t(r) \approx \alpha^2(r_k/r)$, $r_p < r < r_s$, $\alpha = c_k/a_0$, where c_k is the 2D cone/kink wave velocity in materials coordinate system. Determining $\varepsilon_t(r_p)$ and equating to the fracture strain of the material one can determine the perforation velocity of the membrane. A summary of 1D fiber theory and 2D membrane theory can be found in Ref. Haque et al., 2017 [2] and is presented in Appendix A.

Figure 1: Nomenclature for Phoenix and Porwal (P&P, 2003) [1] 2-D Membrane Theory for Isotropic Materials. 1D axial/implosion wave velocity, $a_0 = \sqrt{E/\rho}$. Haque et al., 2017 [2].

In case of orthotropic thin-composite laminates, the use of 2D membrane theory is inadequate and thus finite element models have been developed and validated in computing the cone wave velocities (c_k) for ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) soft-ballistic sub-laminates (SBSL) [2].

Thin-composite laminates have high in-plane and shear moduli and under transverse impact exhibits cone wave propagation superimposed on out-off-plane bending waves. In this study, cone

wave velocity and bending wave velocities have been computationally determined for plain-weave (PW) S-2 Glass/SC15 (814 g/m^2 , 24 oz/yd^2 , 5×5 tows/in, 0.6 mm per one layer 1L) composites subjected to transverse impact velocity less the perforation velocities in the thickness range 1.20 mm (2L) $< H_C < 4.80 \text{ mm}$ (8L). In Ref. Gama & Gillespie, 2017 [3]; materials and modeling parameters of a progressive composite damage model MAT162 in LS-DYNA has been validated with ballistic experiments and will be used in this paper (Appendix B). A tension-shear damage equation in MAT162 uses a new punch-shear strength ($\text{SFS}=\text{X}_3^{\text{PSS}}$) in simulating the perforation failure of a thin-section composite laminate.

Finite element models of 2L, 4L, 6L, & 8L laminates of dimensions $974\text{mm} \times 974\text{mm}$ have been developed with finer mesh ($0.53\text{mm} \sim 3.7\text{mm}$) in the central $178\text{mm} \times 178\text{mm}$ region with 3 through-thickness elements for every 2 layers (3 TTE/ 2L) with free boundary condition (BC). A 50cal RCC steel projectile of is used for all impact analyses (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Finite Element Models for Perforation Mechanics Study.

Figure 3: Cone/Kink Wave Propagation in Thin-Section Composites. Haque & Haque, 2025 [4].

Figure 4: Bending Wave Propagation in Thin-Section Composites. Haque & Haque, 2025 [4].

Propagation of cone/kink wave and bending wave are presented in Figs. 3 & 4 from which the time history of cone/kink waves and bending waves have been calculated and an exponential model has been used to calculate the regression parameters (Fig. 5).

$$\bar{c}_k(t) = \bar{c}_{k\infty} + [\bar{c}_{k\infty} - \bar{c}_k(0)] \exp(-t/\tau_k) \quad (1a)$$

$$c_B(t) = c_{B\infty} + [c_{B\infty} - c_B(0)] \exp(-t/\tau_B) \quad (1b)$$

Where, $\bar{c}_{k\infty} = 260 - 7.5H_C$, $\bar{c}_{k\infty}$ is in m/s, H_C is in mm, $\tau_k = 42.2 \mu s$, $\bar{c}_{k\infty} - \bar{c}_k(0) = 212.4$ m/s, $c_{B\infty} = 290$ m/s, $c_{B\infty} - c_B(0) = 505$ m/s, and $\tau_B = 28.6 \mu s$. Eq. (1a) can be integrated to determine the $r_k(t) = r_p + \int_0^t \bar{c}_k(t) dt$. Eq. (1) is essential in writing integral momentum and energy equations and will be presented elsewhere. Perforation mechanics and ballistics of PW S-2 Glass/SC15 thin-section composites are presented in Fig. 6.

Figure 5: Variation of Cone/Kink and Bending Wave Velocity. Haque & Haque, 2025 [4].

Figure 6: Perforation Mechanics and Ballistics of Thin Laminates. Haque & Haque, 2025 [4]

LS-DYNA stochastic simulations have been performed on square laminates (178mm x 178mm, all edges perfectly clamped BC) in predicting the residual velocity V_R as a function of impact velocity V_I (Fig. 6b) and Haque-Gillespie (H-G, 2015) [5] ballistic equation Eq. (2) is used to determine the ballistic limit velocity V_{BL} and model parameters, i.e., H-G jump velocity V_T , Lambert [6] parameter β^* , and H-G scaling parameter ζ (Table 1). Perforation V_{BL} as a function of H_C shows a power-law behavior $V_{BL} = 80 H_C^{0.6}$ (Fig. 6b). Further discussion on perforation mechanics and ballistics will be presented elsewhere.

$$V_R = [V_T^2 + \beta^*(\zeta V_I^2 - V_{BL}^2)]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

No. of Layers	Thickness, H_C , mm	V_T , m/s	β^*	ζ	V_{BL} , m/s
2L	1.20	4.64	0.895	0.999	85.9
4L	2.40	11.42	0.887	0.999	138.5
6L	3.60	20.80	0.829	0.956	169.6
8L	4.80	30.73	0.669	0.982	199.6

Table 1: 2L-8L Residual Velocity Plots with Ballistic Limits.

2 BALLISTIC PERFORATION AND PENETRATION DAMAGE MECHANISMS

In Ref. Gama & Gillespie, 2017 [3], ballistic experiments with a 101.6mm circular support span and perfectly clamped BC have been conducted on 22L ($H_C=13.2\text{mm}$) and 33L ($H_C=19.8\text{mm}$) with 50cal RCC and 50cal FSP projectiles, respectively (Fig. 7). The ballistic damage modes & mechanisms identified are: (i) deep penetration on the impact side, (ii) plug formation under the projectile, (iii) interlaminar delamination, (iv) tension-shear perforation damage in a thin delaminated rear-portion of the laminate. In order to understand these energy dissipating ballistic damage mechanisms, the author has developed a series of quasi-static (QS) and ballistic experimental methodologies; i.e., (a) QS punch-shear test (QS-PST), (b) QS indentation (QSI) or QS punch-crush test (QS-PCT), (c) ballistic perforation test, and (d) depth of penetration (DoP) test.

Figure 7: Ballistic Damage Mechanisms. Gama & Gillespie, 2017 [3].

3 QS-PST AND QSI EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

To quantify the energy dissipating ballistic damage mechanisms, a QS punch-shear test (QS-PST) experimental methodology (Fig. 8) has been developed by the author where a perfectly clamped laminate is subjected to transverse loading of a RCC punch (D_P) while varying the support span to punch diameter ratio ($\text{SPR}=D_S/D_P$) [7]. It has been shown that the ballistic damage mechanisms can be simulated and quantified by varying the SPR in the range $1.2 < \text{SPR} < 8$ under load-unload-reload experimental methodology [8]. A punch-shear based penetration model of ballistic impact has been developed in Ref. [8] which can predict 97% of ballistic limit energy (Fig. 9). Punch-shear strength (X_3^{PSS}) of a composite has been defined by the author as:

$$X_3^{PSS} = \lim_{\text{SPR} \rightarrow 1} F_P^{\max} / \pi D_P H_C \quad (3)$$

Figure 8: Quasi-Static Punch Shear Test (QS-PST) Experimental Methodology. Ref. [7].

Figure 9: A QS Punch-Shear based Model of Ballistic Penetration. Gama & Gillespie, 2008 [8].

Figure 10: QS Punch-Crush Test (QS-PCT) or QS Indentation (QSI) Experiment. Refs. [7-9].

A quasi-static punch-crush test (QS-PCT, SPR=0) or quasi-static indentation (QSI) experimental methodology has been developed by the author in Refs. [7-9].

$$X_3^{PCS} = 4F_P^{max} / \pi D_P^2 \tag{4}$$

Punch crush-strength (X_3^{PCS}) is defined by Eq. (4) which is a function of composite fiber volume fraction (FVF) and resin yield strength (Fig. 5, Ref. [9]). X_3^{PCS} is used in MAT162 as parameter SFC

to model this important damage mechanisms; and defines the threshold velocity of penetration in the depth of penetration (DoP) analysis methodology.

4 PENETRATION MECHANICS OF THICK-SECTION COMPOSITES

In addition to 2L, 4L, 6L, & 8L perforation simulations; and 11L, 22L, & 33L ballistic simulations in Ref. [3]; additional high velocity impact simulations on 44L to 88L ($H_c = 26.4\text{mm}$ to 52.8mm) composite laminates (Fig. 11) using experimentally determined MAT162 parameters $SFS = X_3^{PSS}$ & $SFC = X_3^{PCS}$ are computationally determined softening [7] and rate parameters [3] (Table B1, Appendix B). Based on the observations of the 88L penetration simulations, Haque & Gillespie, 2014 [10] have identified four phases of ballistic penetration (Fig. 12), i.e., (i) Penetration or P-Phase (0 to $30 \mu s$), (ii) Transition or T-Phase (30 to $60 \mu s$), (iii) Perforation of F-Phase (60 to $140 \mu s$), & (iv) Retraction or R-Phase (140 to $300 \mu s$).

Figure 11: Penetration of 44L to 88L Thick-Section Composites.

Figure 12: Ballistic Penetration or P-Phase (0 to $30 \mu s$), Transition or T-Phase (30 to $60 \mu s$), and Perforation or F-Phase (60 to $140 \mu s$). Haque & Gillespie, 2014 [10].

The P-Phase represents deep penetration and ejection of crushed particles under the projectile, initiation of delamination, and with near zero particle velocity of the surrounding laminate; which can be characterized by DoP experiments. During the T-Phase, significant particle velocity in the laminate is observed with delamination growth in the laminate with continued deep penetration. The end of T-Phase and beginning of F-Phase is when the penetration ceases, and the material ahead of the projectile attains the same velocity as the projectile. During F-Phase, the remaining laminate perforates under tension-shear. A thick-section laminate is defined which shows all three phase of penetration, while an intermediate-thickness laminate is defined which shows the T-phase and F-phase. A thin-section laminate is defined which only shows the F-Phase. While thick-section and intermediate-thickness laminates can be characterized by high velocity ballistic limit (HVBL) experiments, the thin-section laminates can be also be characterized by high velocity ballistic perforation (HVBP) experiments.

5 DEPTH OF PENETRATION (DOP) EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

In a DoP experiment (Fig. 13), a finite-thickness target is clamped on a rigid ‘solid support’ using another rigid ‘cover plate.’ Upon the impact of a RCC projectile on the target at an impact velocity V_I , the projectile penetrates, compresses, and crushes the composite under the projectile, the crushed particles eject through the penetration cavity around the projectile in a direction opposite to the projectile motion, and finally the projectile stops inside the target at a penetration depth of d_p ; which is plotted as a function of V_I and is also known as classic penetration-resistance test. The author has developed [12] an energy based DoP model (Eq. 5) where the experimental data provides two DoP parameters: (i) V_{TH} – the threshold velocity of penetration, and (ii) τ_{DOP} – the characteristic time of DoP

$$d_p = \tau_{DOP} (V_I - V_{TH}) \tag{5}$$

Figure 13: DoP Experimental Methodology.

Figure 14: DoP Experimental, Theoretical, and Computational Modeling Methodology.

From the energy based DoP model (Fig. 14a), the projectile instantaneous rigid body velocity $\dot{z}(t)$ (Eq. 6a), the hydrodynamic pressure $p_H(t)$ of the crushed particles under the projectile (Eq. 6b) and the penetration resistance force $F(t)$ on the projectile (Eq. 6c) can be derived.

$$\dot{z}(t) = V_i \exp(-t/\tau_{DoP}) \quad (5a)$$

$$p_H(t) = (\rho_p H_p / \tau_{DoP}) V_i \exp(-t/\tau_{DoP}) \quad (5b)$$

$$F_p(t) = (m_p / \tau_{DoP}) V_i \exp(-t/\tau_{DoP}) \quad (5c)$$

Punch-crush and punch-shear are two unique damage mechanisms of the DoP experiments on thick-section composites (Fig. 14b). While punch crush of composites occurs under the projectile, the punch shear occurs along the edge of the projectile. Micromechanical punch crush damage mechanisms are (i) matrix crack, (ii) fiber fracture, (iii) fiber-matrix debonding (iv) hydrodynamic crush of both matrix and fibers; and the micromechanical punch shear damage mechanisms are (a) matrix crack, (b) matrix tension-shear, (c) fiber-matrix debonding, and (d) mode II dominated fiber fracture.

6 SUMMARY

This paper presents the fundamental understanding of the perforation and penetration mechanics of very thick to thin composite laminates developed by the author over the last two decades. In addition, new results on the cone/kink wave and bending wave propagation on thin-section composites have been presented along with stochastic ballistic limit predictions using rate dependent progressive composite damage model MAT162 in LS-DYNA. Two experimental methods for punch-shear & punch-crush developed by the author are also presented. New results of deep penetration of thick-sections composite have been presented and used to define three phases of ballistic penetration, i.e., Penetration (P-), Transition (T-), and Perforation (F-) phases. DoP experimental, theoretical, and computational models developed by the author has also been presented. The methodologies developed here will further be extended to develop an unified theory of ballistic penetration and perforation of composite laminates and left as future work.

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APPENDIX A: THEORY OF TRANSVERSE IMPACT ON FIBERS AND MEMBRANE

Theories of constant velocity transverse impact on 1D-fiber had been developed between 1945 to 1960 by Rakhmatulin and Smith. Following these classic theories, Phoenix and Porwal (P&P, 2003) has developed an axi-symmetric membrane theory for constant velocity transverse impact on an isotropic elastic membrane with a cylindrical projectile. The well-known Smith (1958, 1960) equations considers constant velocity transverse impact on a 1D isotropic fiber. Upon the impact of a projectile with impact velocity V_p , an implosion or axial strain wave of amplitude ε_0 propagates along the fiber between points 'p' and 's' with an axial wave speed of $a_0 = \sqrt{E/\rho}$ followed by a transverse cone wave with a constant cone wave front velocity, $\bar{c}_{k,0}$, at point 'k' with respect to the laboratory frame of coordinate, and forms a constant cone angle γ with the fiber axis at the projectile root at point 'p'. Smith's equations for the explosion strain ε_0 , the cone wave front velocity $\bar{c}_{k,0}$ in laboratory frame of coordinates, the cone wave front velocity $c_{k,0}$ in material coordinates, and the cone root angle γ as a function of constant impact velocity V_p are given by:

$$V_p = a_0 \sqrt{\varepsilon_0(1 + \varepsilon_0) - \left[\sqrt{\varepsilon_0(1 + \varepsilon_0)} - \varepsilon_0 \right]^2} \quad (1a)$$

$$\bar{c}_{k,0} = a_0 \left[\sqrt{\varepsilon_0(1 + \varepsilon_0)} - \varepsilon_0 \right] \quad (1b)$$

$$\frac{c_{k,0}}{a_0} = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_0}{(1 + \varepsilon_0)}} = \alpha_0 \quad (1c)$$

$$\sin \gamma = \frac{V_p}{a_0 \sqrt{\varepsilon_0(1 + \varepsilon_0)}} \quad (1d)$$

In order to express $\varepsilon_0 = \varepsilon_0(V_p, a_0)$, Eq. (1a) have been simplified to:

$$\varepsilon_0 \approx \left(\frac{V_p}{a_0 \sqrt{2}} \right)^{4/3} \quad (1e)$$

Equation (1e) can now be used to evaluate the other Eqs. (1b), (1c) & (1d). Phoenix & Porwal (2003) developed a 2D-membrane theory for isotropic materials where the cone wave velocity starts at 1D value (Eq. 1b & 1c), increases non-linearly with time and essentially forms a plateau. P&P (2003) provided analytical solutions for cone wave velocity \bar{c}_k in laboratory frame of coordinates, and membrane strain $\varepsilon_t(r)$ as follows:

$$\bar{c}_k = c_k + \dot{u}_k = a_0 \left\{ \alpha + \frac{\alpha^2 \left[\ln \alpha - \ln \left\{ 1 - \frac{r_p}{r_k} (1 - \alpha) \right\} - 1 \right]}{1 + \frac{(1 - \alpha)(r_k - r_p)}{\alpha r_k}} \right\} \quad (2a)$$

$$\varepsilon_t(r) \approx \varepsilon_t(r_k) \frac{r_k}{r} \approx \alpha^2 \frac{r_k}{r} \quad r_p < r < r_s \quad (2b)$$

Where, c_k is the kink wave velocity in materials coordinate system, $\dot{u}_k = \dot{u}_k$ is the particle velocity at the kink point 'k', $\alpha = c_k/a_0$, r_p is the radius of the projectile, r_k is the location of the cone wave front at point 'k', and r_s is the location of the implosion wave front at point 's'. The value of α can be determined iteratively using the following formula as described in P&P (2003).

$$\alpha_{n+1} \approx \alpha_0 \left(\frac{r_p}{r_k} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \frac{\left\{ \frac{1}{\alpha_n} \left(\frac{r_k}{r_p} - 1 \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\left\{ \ln \left[1 + \frac{1}{\alpha_n} \left(\frac{r_k}{r_p} - 1 \right) \right] \right\}^{\frac{1}{3}}} \quad (3)$$

Where $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, and $\alpha_0 = c_{k,0}/a_0$. P&P (2003) showed that only two iterations provides quite accurate result, i.e., $\alpha \approx \alpha_2$. Once the value of α can be determined using Eqs. (3), (1c) & (1e); then Eqs. (2a) and (2b) can be evaluated. Eq. (2a) has been further reduced for 1D case in P&P (2003) to:

$$\bar{c}_{k,0} = c_{k,0} + \dot{u}_{k,0} = \alpha_0 a_0 (1 - \alpha_0 + \alpha_0^2) \quad (4)$$

Eq. (4) provides a slightly smaller value of $\bar{c}_{k,0}$ as compared to Eq. (1b). P&P, 2003, showed that the cone/kink wave velocity for the 2D membrane, c_k , is equal to $c_{k,0}$ at $r_k = r_p$, increases to a maximum at around $r_k = 2r_p$, then reduces to a plateau value (higher than $c_{k,0}$) for $r_k \gg 2r_p$ for a constant value of ε_0 . It is also important to mention that the 2D membrane cone/kink wave speed increases with the increase in ε_0 , that is with impact speed V_p . In Ref. [8], it has been shown that for isotropic 1D fiber and 2D membrane, a finite element model can capture the theoretical physics of deformation with good correlations. We will use these 1D and 2D equations to verify the finite element models of transverse impact on thin-section composite plates.

APPENDIX B: MAT162 INPUT PROPERTIES & PARAMETERS FOR PW S-2 GLASS/SC15 COMPOSITES

MID	RO, kg/m ³	EA, GPa	EB, GPa	EC, GPa	PRBA	PRCA	PRCB
162	1850.00	27.50	27.50	11.80	0.11	0.18	0.18
GAB, GPa	GBC, GPa	GCA, GPa					
2.90	2.14	2.14					
SAT, MPa	SAC, MPa	SBT, MPa	SBC, MPa	SCT, MPa	SFC, MPa	SFS, MPa	SAB, MPa
604.00	291.00	604.00	291.00	58.00	850.00	300.00	75.00
SBC, MPa	SCA, MPa	SFFC	PHIC	E_LIMT	S_DELM		
58.00	58.00	0.300	10	0.200	1.200		
OMGMX	ECRSH	EEXPN	CRATE1	AM1			
0.999	0.001	4.500	0.030	2.00			
AM2	AM3	AM4	CRATE2	CRATE3	CRATE4		
2.00	0.50	0.20	0.000	0.030	0.030		

Table B1. MAT162 Input Properties and Parameters for S-2 Glass/SC15 Composite [3]